

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS TO ENHANCE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE CUTTING METALWORKING PROCESS

D.V. Sarkisyan

Doctoral students of Moscow State University of Technology "Stankin" (MSUT "Stankin")

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14978251>

Abstract. *The given article discusses the application of artificial neural networks (ANNs) to enhance the efficiency of the cutting metalworking process. The main challenges related to selecting optimal processing conditions, diagnosing tool conditions and adaptive process control are outlined. A method for modeling cutting parameters based on a multilayer perceptron is presented, which allows for the prediction of cutting force and temperature in the cutting zone. The feasibility of using neural network algorithms for optimizing technological parameters, controlling tool wear and predictive maintenance is substantiated. Methods for optimizing neural network training algorithms, including network structure selection, adaptive weight adjustment, data normalization, and feature selection, are discussed. In the given research the application of these methods that enhances prediction accuracy, reduces training time, and lowers production costs are described as well. In the future, the integration of neural network technologies into CNC systems and adaptive control opens up new opportunities for automating metalworking processes.*

Keywords: *network structure selection, adaptive weight adjustment, data normalization, multilayer perceptron.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that the cutting metalworking is one of the key technological processes in mechanical engineering, determining the quality and cost of the produced products. With the development of automated production, the introduction of numerically controlled machines and the use of new materials, the requirements for processing accuracy, tool durability and economic efficiency have significantly increased. One of the most important tasks is selecting optimal cutting conditions that minimize tool wear, improve processing quality and reduce energy consumption.

However, traditional methods of calculating technological parameters do not always account for the complex nonlinear dependencies between various factors influencing the cutting process.

Certainly, in recent years, artificial intelligence methods, particularly artificial neural networks have been actively applied in industry. These networks allow for the analysis of large volumes of data and the identification of optimal solutions based on accumulated experience. The use of neural network technologies in metalworking opens up new possibilities for predicting key process parameters such as temperature and cutting force, diagnosing tool condition, and adaptive process control. Due to the ability of neural networks to account for complex interrelationships between processing parameters, their use can significantly increase productivity, reduce tool costs and minimize the influence of the human factor.

Solution to the problem with the use of artificial neural networks

It is worth mentioning that the effectiveness of neural network modeling has been confirmed in several studies. Thus, J.F. Briceno, H. El-Mounayri and S. Mukhopadhyay [1] applied artificial neural networks for modeling the end milling process, while D. Mandal, S.K. Pal, and P. Saha [2] used them for modeling electrical discharge machining. In the works of H-Y Kim and J-H Ahn [3], the application of neural network methods for diagnosing drilling based on spindle power consumption data was discussed. M. Korosec, J. Balic, and J. Kopac [4] utilized artificial neural networks to assess the machinability of free surfaces of the workpiece. The research by P.G. Benardos, S. Mosialos and G.-C. Vosniakos [5] demonstrated the possibility of predicting elastic deformations of the workpiece during turning, while S. Arul, L. Vijayaraghavan, and S.K. Malhotra [6] applied neural network models for online monitoring of workpiece quality during drilling.

Building a Neural Network Model

In order to build a neural network model, it is essential to select the optimal network topology and determine the set of input parameters. According to the analysis of the main types of neural networks conducted by D.E. Dimla [7], the most efficient architecture for predicting cutting parameters is a multilayer perceptron with one hidden layer. The input data for such a model include cutting speed, feed rate, cutting depth, material thermal conductivity, rake angle, and tool nose radius. The network predicts cutting force and temperature in the cutting zone, allowing for real-time adjustment of processing parameters to improve efficiency.

Definitely, local literature also presents studies in this area. Systems for cutting tool control during precision turning based on machine vision were proposed in [8], methods for diagnosing tool wear through sound signals are described in [9], and the use of a neural network approach to assess the surface roughness of a workpiece during turning was discussed in works [10-14].

For improving the accuracy of neural network models and accelerate their training, methods for optimizing the network structure and learning algorithms have been proposed. In the research by R.K. Jain and V.K. Jain [15], a methodology for selecting optimal abrasive jet machining parameters was proposed, while H. El-Mounayri, H. Kishawy, and J. Briceno [16] developed an integrated system for optimizing spherical end milling on CNC machines. Further studies have shown that the use of hybrid algorithms combining the backpropagation method and adaptive weight adjustment significantly reduces training time and improves prediction accuracy.

Optimization of Neural Network Training Algorithms

What is more important, the optimization of artificial neural network (ANN) training algorithms plays a crucial role in enhancing their effectiveness in metalworking applications. The main goal is to reduce the training time of the network, minimize computational costs, and increase the accuracy of predicting cutting process parameters. Achieving these goals is possible through the selection of the optimal network architecture, improvement of learning methods, and proper selection of input data.

One of the key steps in optimization is choosing the structure of the neural network. An overly complex architecture with a large number of hidden layers and neurons leads to an increase in training time and the possibility of overfitting, where the network memorizes the training data but cannot generalize well for new cases. On the other hand, an overly simple network is unable to accurately model the cutting process. An optimal solution is to use a multilayer perceptron with one hidden layer, containing a number of neurons corresponding to the number of input parameters or slightly exceeding it. Practice shows that for tasks such as predicting temperature and cutting

force, a hidden layer with 12-20 neurons is sufficient, which allows the network to effectively process input data without excessive complexity.

Optimization of Neural Network Training Methods

In addition to selecting the network structure, significant attention must be given to the training method. One of the most widely used algorithms is backpropagation of errors, but its drawback is the need for a large number of iterations and high computational complexity. For accelerating the training process, the method of adaptive weight adjustment in hidden and output layers is applied.

Surprisingly, this method is based on analyzing the direction of error change: if the error increases at the next step of training, the weight coefficient is adjusted in the opposite direction. This approach allows for faster convergence to optimal weights, reducing the number of iterations and thus decreasing the training time.

Another optimization approach is the use of hybrid training methods, which combine different algorithms. For example, combining the gradient descent method with stochastic optimization techniques, such as Rumelhart algorithm or the Levenberg-Marquardt method, can significantly speed up training and increase the network's accuracy. Stochastic optimization helps avoid local minima of the error, which is particularly important when dealing with nonlinear dependencies in the cutting process.

Additionally, preprocessing of data also plays an essential role. Artificial neural networks are sensitive to the scale of input parameters, so normalizing the data before training helps accelerate the process of finding optimal weights. For example, rescaling cutting parameters (such as speed, feed, and depth) to the range [0,1] or [-1,1] improves the convergence of the algorithm and reduces the likelihood that some input parameters will dominate the learning process.

Feature Selection and Optimization of Neural Networks for Metalworking

Another important aspect is featuring selection. The input data should only contain parameters that significantly influence the processing results. Sensitivity coefficient analysis shows that key parameters for predicting cutting temperature and cutting force include cutting speed, feed rate, depth of cut, thermal conductivity of the material, rake angle, and tool nose radius. Excluding irrelevant variables reduces the size of the input layer of the network and decreases computational load.

Moreover, an additional optimization method is reducing the number of training examples while maintaining high prediction accuracy. This can be achieved through active learning methods, where the network is initially trained on a small dataset, and then cases with the largest prediction errors are analyzed. Subsequently, new training examples are selectively chosen from areas where the network shows the greatest errors. This allows for minimizing the sample size without sacrificing accuracy.

Thus, optimizing neural network algorithms for metalworking involves several key directions: selecting the optimal network architecture, improving learning methods, preprocessing data, selecting the most significant input parameters, and reducing the redundant volume of the training dataset. A comprehensive approach to these tasks increases the accuracy of cutting parameter prediction, reduces computational costs, and ensures more efficient process control. Further development of neural network algorithms is possible through integration with other artificial intelligence methods, such as fuzzy logic, genetic algorithms, and Bayesian analysis, which will open up new prospects for automation and optimization in metalworking.

Conclusions

The use of artificial neural networks in machining processes significantly increases production efficiency by optimizing cutting modes, monitoring tool wear, and adaptive process control. Neural network models have the ability to account for complex nonlinear relationships between technological parameters and allow for the prediction of key process characteristics, such as cutting force and temperature.

The research confirmed that using a multilayer perceptron with one hidden layer and six input parameters (cutting speed, feed rate, cutting depth, material thermal conductivity, rake angle, and tool nose radius) enables more accurate determination of optimal processing conditions. This contributes to improved processing quality, reduced tool wear, and lower replacement costs.

Certainly, tool condition diagnosis using neural network algorithms has also proven effective. Methods of acoustic signal analysis, consumed power, and vibrational characteristics allow for the timely detection of deviations in the operation of cutting tools, predicting their wear, and minimizing the risk of failure. The implementation of such technologies in automated CNC systems opens up opportunities for creating intelligent monitoring systems capable of adapting processing parameters in real-time.

By summarizing it should be suggested that artificial neural networks represent a promising tool for automating and optimizing machining processes. Their integration into production systems allows for improved prediction accuracy of technological parameters, reduced tool costs and energy consumption, as well as increased overall stability of machining processes. Further development of neural network technologies is possible through integration with other artificial intelligence methods, such as fuzzy logic and genetic algorithms, which will enable the creation of more flexible and adaptive control systems.

REFERENCES

1. Briceno J.F. Selecting an artificial neural network for efficient modeling and accurate simulation of the milling process / J.F. Briceno, H. El-Mounayri, S. Mukhopadhyay // *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*. – 2002. – Vol. 42, №6. - P. 663-674.
2. Mandal D. Modeling of electrical discharge machining process using back propagation neural network and multi-objective optimization using non-dominating sorting genetic algorithm-II / D. Mandal, S.K. Pal, P. Saha // *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. – 2007. – Vol. 186, №1-3. – P. 154-162.
3. Kim H.-Y. Chip disposal state monitoring in drilling using neural network-based spindle motor power sensing / H.-Y. Kim, J.-H. Ahn // *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*. – 2002. – Vol. 42, №10. – P. 1113-1119.
4. Korosec M. Neural network-based manufacturability evaluation of free form machining / M.
5. Korosec, J. Balic, J. Kopac // *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*. – 2005. – Vol. 45, №1. – P. 13-20.
6. Benardos P.G. Prediction of workpiece elastic deflections under cutting forces in turning / P.G. Benardos, S. Mosialos, G.-C. Vosniakos // *Robotics and Computer Integrated Manufacturing*. – 2006. – Vol. 22, №5-6. – P. 505-514.

7. Arul S. Online monitoring of acoustic emission for quality control in drilling of polymeric composites / S. Arul, L. Vijayaraghavan, S.K. Malhotra // *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. – 2007. – Vol. 185, №1-3. – P. 184-190.
8. Cory runyon real-time quality control of the injection molding process using artificial neural networks / Thesis (M.S.)-Brigham Young University. Dept. of Manufacturing Engineering and Engineering Technology. Includes bibliographical references (P. [82]-84).
9. Derivyantsenko A.G., Bovnegra L.V., Krinitsyn D.A., Koss E.V., Fomin A.A. "System of control and methods of tool condition recognition for maintaining their performance." *Scientific Papers of DonNTU. Designing Progressive cutting tool structures and technological equipment*. – 2009. – Pp. 87–94.
10. Vnukov Yu.N. "Modeling tool wear based on wavelet transformation of sound signals." *Artificial Intelligence*. – 2008. – N. 1. – Pp. 73–79.
11. Medvedev V.V., Medvedev V.S. "Features of diagnostics of machining quality using intelligent systems." *Bulletin of the Donbas State Engineering Academy*. – 2008, N. 3E (14). – Pp. 131–135.
12. Tsao C.C. Tool wear and surface roughness prediction using an artificial neural network (ANN) in turning steel under minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) / C.C. Tsao, H. Hochen // *Engineering and Technology*. – 2010. – №62. – P. 830-839.
13. Ozel T. Predictive modeling of surface roughness and tool wear in hard turning using regression and neural networks / T. Ozel, Y. Karpat // *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*. – 2005. – Vol. 45, №4-5. – P. 467-479.
14. Abburi N.R. A knowledge-based system for the prediction of surface roughness in turning process / N.R. Abburi, U.S. Dixit // *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*. – 2006. – Vol. 22. – №4. – P. 363-372.
15. Jain R.K. Optimum selection of machining conditions in abrasive flow machining using neural network / R.K. Jain, V.K. Jain // *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. – 2000. – Vol. 108, №1. – P. 62-67.
16. El-Mounayri H. Optimization of CNC ball end milling: a neural network-based model / H. ElMounayri, H. Kishawy, J. Briceno // *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. – 2005. – Vol. 166, №1. – P. 50-62.